

INFLUENCE OF EMPLOYEE COMPETENCE AND EMPLOYEE EMPOWERMENT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE: ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AS MEDIATION

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the direct effect of Employee Competence and Employee Empowerment on Employee Performance with the role of Organizational Commitment as Mediation. Data obtained from banking sector workers PT. BRI Soekarno Hatta Malang Branch Office. Analysis of the data used is statistical inferential Structural Equation Model (SEM) using Partial Least Square (PLS) with WarpPLS 6.0 Software. Research findings show that Employee Competence and Employee Empowerment have a significant and positive effect on Organizational Commitment. Employee Competence and Employee Empowerment have a significant and positive effect on employee performance. Organizational commitment has a significant and positive effect on employee performance. Organizational Commitment mediates the effect of employee competence and employee empowerment on employee performance.

Keywords: Employee Competence, Employee Empowerment, Organizational Commitment Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

In the Industry 4.0 era as an era of digitalization, all aspects of life are required to be able to adapt to the development of that era. Within the organization the adjustment is made by changing the manual process to a comprehensive digital platform. Human resources, which are one of the key factors in facing the development of digital technology, cannot be separated from the impact of the development of the digital era. The HR function in the Industrial 4.0 era is becoming increasingly strategic and important in business organizations, thus requiring a more comprehensive, structured, and measurable and standardized HR practitioner development system. (Triyonggo et al, 2015).

Human resource development in the Industry 4.0 era must refer to work competency standards. The development of industry 4.0 requires workers to have special skills and be more skilled in various fields. Robbins and Judges. (2015) argues that competence is the ability or capacity of a person to do various tasks in a job, where this ability is determined by two factors of intellectual ability and physical ability. Thierauf (2008) states that the competence of human resources is built from the substance of knowledge, skills, experience, attitudes and work skills. High competence is used to increase organizational commitment and individual performance. Employees with good and appropriate competencies will be able to understand what must be done and what their functions are in the job. A good understanding of the functions and adequate competencies of an employee will foster a high commitment to the organization.

Past Research found Employee Competence has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment (Rantesalu et al, 2016; Martini et al, 2018; Rumawas, 2011; Sujana, 2012; and Fadli et al, 2012). In contrast to the research results of Alkurni et al (2020) which found evidence that there was no influence of intellectual competence on organizational commitment. Furthermore, several studies show that competence has an effect on employee performance (Mugianto and Sulasmi, 2016); Martini et al, 2018; Lotunani et al, 2014; Adam and Kamase, 2019; Obiekwe et al, 2019). In contrast to the research of Kotamena et al (2020) which found evidence that the level of competence of professional human resources did not have a significant relationship with employee performance.

Giving empowerment to employees is one step in managing human resources to increase employee commitment and performance, because empowerment is a trust given by superiors to subordinates in full, with the hope that employees can be responsible for carrying out the tasks entrusted to them. Decicco et al. (2006) argue that providing opportunities for structural work empowerment for employees (ie empowerment focused on increasing employee engagement) will lead to positive attitudes that encourage employees to achieve commitment to the organization. Furthermore, Duvall (1999) argues that the success of a job performance is a consequence of empowerment. Thomas and Velthouse (1990) illustrate that an empowered employee will make every effort to get the job done. Meyerson and Dewettick (2012) explain that if employee empowerment is carried out continuously, performance and opportunities increase as participation and involvement in decision making.

Several previous researchers found evidence that employee empowerment has an effect on organizational commitment (Abdullah et al, 2015; Hanaysha, 2016; Murray & Holmes, 2021). This is different from the research findings of Sulistiono et al (2019) which found evidence of empowerment not having a significant effect on organizational commitment. Fernandez Research, 2011; Sumardi, 2019; Hani, Yassine and Rand, 2019; shows that there is a significant effect of employee empowerment on employee performance. Meanwhile, Bose's research (2018) shows different results, namely empowerment has no effect on employee performance.

Employees who have a strong organizational commitment will have different attitudes compared to employees who have a weak organizational commitment. Strong organizational commitment will result in work performance, low absenteeism and low employee turnover. According to Robins (2008) commitment is a form of identification, loyalty and involvement expressed by employees towards the organization or work unit. The success of a person's performance is determined by the level of competence, professionalism, and also his commitment to the work he is doing. Employees with high commitment are more comfortable at work, loyal, and participate so that they show optimal performance results. Empirically, the effect of organizational commitment on employee performance, found in research by Rafiei et al (2014) found evidence that organizational commitment has a significant positive effect on work performance. In addition, this study also shows that the three dimensions of Organizational Commitment, namely: Affective, Continuing, and Normative, have a significant positive effect on work performance. This is different from the findings of Kaplan & Kaplan's (2018) research which examines the effect of Organizational Commitment on

Performance on Manufacturing Companies in Turkey. The results showed that affective commitment has a positive and significant effect on performance. On the other hand, continuance commitment and normative commitment have no significant effect on performance

The inconsistent results of previous studies motivate researchers to re-examine competence and empowerment of performance in one research model. The aim is to contribute to the repertory of empirical findings in an effort to test existing models of explanatory human resource development theory, as well as to test the consistency of previous findings. In overcoming the research gap, in this study organizational commitment variable is used as a mediating variable. This is based on the opinion of Laksmi (2010) that commitment has a relationship with performance so it is important for organizations to grow employee commitment. Commitment to the organization has the meaning of concern and ability that synergizes in influencing the success of the organization in achieving its goals

Specifically, this study aims: first, to examine and analyze the effect of Competence and Empowerment on employee performance. Second, examine and analyze the effect of Competence and Empowerment on organizational commitment. Third, examine and analyze the effect of organizational commitment on employee performance. Fourth, examine and analyze organizational commitment to mediate the effect of employee empowerment and competence on employee performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Integrating Employee Competency with Organizational Commitment and Employee Performance

Ability is an important thing to be able to complete a job in addition to motivation and opportunity. If an employee does not have the ability even though he gets the opportunity and is supported by high motivation, of course it will be difficult to complete work with standardized quality, quantity and time. Robbins and Judge (2015) argue that competence refers to an individual's capacity to perform various tasks in a job. Basically abilities can be divided into two major groups, namely intellectual abilities and physical abilities.

Human resource competence is built from the substance of knowledge, skills, experience, attitudes and work skills. High competence is used to increase organizational commitment and individual performance (Thierauf, 2008). Empirical evidence shows that competence has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment and employee performance (Kanfer et al., 2010; Sujana, 2012). Furthermore, Rantesalu et al, 2016; Martini et al, 2018 tested and analyzed the effect of employee competence on organizational commitment. The research findings show that employee competence has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment.

According to Spencer (2007) to achieve high performance, both for technicians and professionals, salespeople, helping and human service, while managers and entrepreneurs need

competencies which include, competencies: achievement and action, serving, leading, managing, thinking, and a good personality. Furthermore, Mangkunegara, (2008) high ability requires ability (ability), skills (expertise) and knowledge (knowledge). So as to get maximum performance. Thus it can be explained in theory that employee competence will improve employee performance.

Empirical evidence of the relationship of competence to employee performance is found in Lotunani's research (2014) which examines and analyzes employee performance in the Kendari city government. The results show a significant effect of employee competence on employee performance. Rantesalu (2016) also tested and analyzed employee performance at different locations, finding the results that there was a real impact of competence on performance. Murgianto and Sulasmi's research (2016) proves the impact of employee work competence on employee performance. Martini et al (2018) and Renyut (2017) also prove that employee performance increases with employee competence.

Based on above literature and arguments, following hypotheses are generated

Hypothesis 1: Employee Competence has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment.

Hypothesis 2: Employee Competence has a significant effect on Employee Performance

Integrating Employee Empowerment with Organizational Commitment and Employee Performance

Wibowo (2012) explains empowerment as a process to make people more empowered or more capable to solve their own problems by giving trust and authority, thus fostering a sense of responsibility. Abadi and Chegini (2013) argue that employee empowerment is one of the most effective techniques to increase employee productivity and optimal use of individual or group capacities and abilities in accordance with organizational goals. Decicco et al. (2006) said that providing opportunities for structural work empowerment for employees (ie empowerment focused on increasing employee engagement) will lead to positive attitudes that encourage them to achieve commitment to the organization. Empirical evidence of the relationship between empowerment and organizational commitment is found in Abdullah et al. (2015), Hanaysha Research (2016) and Murray & Holmes Research (2021) which found evidence of employee empowerment having a significant effect on organizational commitment.

Thomas and Velthouse (1990) argue that employee empowerment can be illustrated as individuals who have been motivated and committed and have great responsibility in carrying out all efforts at a higher level. Furthermore, according to Meyerson & Dewettinck (2012) empowerment is an effort to improve performance and opportunities to participate and be involved in decision making, empowering employees to become a motivational practice that has a purpose. So, theoretically, employee empowerment improves employee performance.

Sedarmayanti (2007) argued human resource empowerment is a process of business activities to further empower "human resources" through change and human development itself, in the form of abilities, trust, authority, and responsibility and the framework of implementing organizational activities to improve performance as expected. Many studies have found that

empowerment has a significant effect on employee performance (Fernandez and Moldogaziev, 2011; Karatepe, 2013; Guest, 2014, Sattar et al., 2015; Guan and Frenkel, 2018; Yin, 2018,)

Based on above literature and arguments, following hypotheses are generated

Hypothesis 3: Employee Empowerment has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment.

Hypothesis 4: Employee Empowerment has a significant effect on Employee Performance

Integrating Organizational Commitment and Employee Performance

Organizational commitment relates to the extent to which an employee favors a particular organization and its goals, and intends to maintain membership in the organization. Employees who have high involvement in work have no desire to leave the company and in this case are the basic capital to encourage high productivity. Mathis and Jackson (2006) state that organizational commitment is reflected in the degree to which employees believe and accept organizational goals and desire to stay with the organization.

Employees who have high commitment can show optimal performance. Someone who joins the organization is required to have a commitment in him. Organizational commitment not only means passive loyalty, but also involves an active relationship and the desire of employees to make a meaningful contribution to the organization. The higher the commitment, the higher the tendency of a person to be directed to actions that are in accordance with employee performance standards (Chughtai & Zafar, 2006). Empirical evidence of the relationship of organizational commitment to employee performance is found in Ireffin & Mechanic (2014) and Rafiei et al (2014) find evidence that organizational commitment has a significant positive effect on performance

Based on above literature and arguments, following hypotheses are generated

Hypothesis 5: Organizational Commitment has a significant effect on Employee Performance

Integrating Organizational Commitment with Employee Competence, Employee Empowerment and Employee Performance

Sedarmayanti (2007) states that competence is closer to the ability or capability that is applied and produces employees or leaders or officials who show maximum performance. Employee performance is more or less influenced by the commitment of the employee himself. Competence will be in vain if employees do not have a high commitment to the organization. Competencies such as knowledge, education and skills will be much better if there is commitment from employees such as pleasure in doing tasks and concern for the organization. Thus, the performance of the employee himself will be better. Wibowo (2012) states that competence is an ability to do a job that is based on skills and knowledge and is supported by a work attitude, namely the experience or learning required by the job. Wibowo also stated that competence is a person's ability to work based on skills and knowledge by including individual attitudes in work. It is also important to support competence is the role of experience and learning in carrying out various duties properly and professionally.

Furthermore, Sedarmayanti (2007) argues that employee performance is a translation of performance which means the work of a worker, a management process or an organization as a whole, where the results of the work must be shown concrete evidence and can be measured (compared to predetermined standards). . Employee empowerment plays an important role in increasing employee commitment to achieve something. Empowerment through employee engagement refers to the extent to which employees are fully engaged in their work and the strength of their commitment to the job and the company. So, if employee empowerment is managed properly, it will lead to high work commitment so that employee performance is more optimal and will benefit a company to achieve company goals.

Based on above literature and arguments, following hypotheses are generated

Hypothesis 6: Organizational Commitment mediates the effect of Employee Competence on Employee Performance

Hypothesis 7: Organizational Commitment mediates the effect of Employee Empowerment on Employee Performance

This study develops a conceptual model that shows the relationship of Organizational Commitment as a mediating variable on the relationship between employee competence and employee competence on employee performance as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research model

METHODOLOGY

Samples and Data Collection

The type of research used is Explanatory Research, which explains the relationships between research variables through hypothesis testing. The population in this study were permanent employees who had worked for at least 1 year in the marketing/marketing department of BRI at the Soekarno Hatta Malang Branch Office with a total of 97 respondents. The sampling technique used proportional random sampling. Data collection is done by sending a list of questions to respondents related to research via Google form.

Measurement

The variables used in this study consisted of employee competencies consisting of 6 indicators developed by Fernandez and Moldogaziev (2011) and Potnuru et al. (2019), Employee empowerment with 5 indicators developed by Potnuru et al. (2019). Employee performance consists of 6 indicators developed Dharma (2005) and Paais (2018), Organizational Commitment consists of 6 indicators developed by Mayer and Allen (1993). This study uses a Likert scale with an alternative score of 1-5. Respondents were asked to rate the questionnaire items with seven scale (Strongly disagree: score 1, disagree: score 2, Neutral: score 3, Agree: score 4, Strongly Agree: score 5)

Estimating Model

This study employed Structural Equation Model (SEM) using Partial Least Square (PLS) with component-based or variance-based structural equations (SEM). In the analysis using PLS there are 2 things to do, namely: First, assessing the outer model or measurement model. Second, assessing the Inner Model or Structural Model

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Table 1: Combined Loading dan Cross Loading

	Competence	empower	Organisational Comitment	Pefromance	P value
Competence1	0.647	-0.035	0.069	-0.151	<0.001
Competence2	0.435	0.153	0.226	0.294	<0.001
Competence3	0.482	0.119	-0.128	0.325	<0.001
Competence4	0.538	-0.328	-0.109	-0.155	<0.001
Competence5	0.621	0.128	-0.097	-0.117	<0.001
Competence6	0.647	-0.007	0.058	-0.049	<0.001
Empower1	0.115	0.714	0.248	-0.402	<0.001
Empower 2	-0.286	0.643	-0.428	0.53	<0.001
Empower 3	-0.081	0.613	-0.138	0.122	<0.001
Empower 4	0.039	0.753	0.116	-0.114	<0.001
Empower 5	0.301	0.406	0.235	-0.105	<0.001
Orgcomm1	-0.104	-0.022	0.748	0.21	<0.001
Orgcomm 2	0.001	-0.15	0.633	0.096	<0.001
Orgcomm 3	0.035	0.074	0.759	0.017	<0.001
Orgcomm 4	0.115	0.099	0.761	-0.174	<0.001
Orgcomm 5	0.151	-0.209	0.657	0.081	<0.001
Orgcomm 6	-0.189	0.162	0.718	-0.211	<0.001
Performance1	-0.047	-0.04	0.128	0.751	<0.001
Performance 2	0.254	-0.181	0.173	0.562	<0.001
Performance 3	-0.156	0.306	-0.176	0.558	<0.001
Performance 4	-0.073	-0.132	-0.123	0.705	<0.001
Performance 5	0.156	0.308	-0.014	0.546	<0.001
Performance 6	-0.11	-0.232	-0.002	0.492	<0.001

From the results of data analysis, it is known that all indicators have a factor value greater than 0.30 (Hair et al. 2010), with a significant value of P value <0.001 so that overall these indicators are able to represent the constructs of Empowerment Employees, Employee Competence, Employee Performance and Organizational Commitment. These criteria are able to assess the validity that the indicator is proven to be a valid construct. The discriminant validity test can be seen from the loading and cross loading values. If the loading value of each indicator on the relevant variable is greater than the cross loading on the other latent variables, it is said to meet discriminant validity.

The next test to evaluate the outer model is to test the reliability of the latent construct as measured by Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability. The construct is declared reliable if the value is above 0.60

Table 2: Cronbach's Alpha Test and Composite Reliability Results

	Cronbachs Alpha	Composite Reliability
Employee Competence	0.671	0.736
Employee Empowerment	0.621	0.767
Organizational Commitment	0.807	0.862
Employee Performance	0.653	0.776

Evaluation of the Structural Model (Inner Model)

The suitability test between the theoretical and empirical models can be seen at the level of Goodness-of-fit statistics. A model is said to be fit if the covariance matrix of a model is the same as the covariance of the data matrix (observed). Model fit indices and P values display the results of ten fit indicators.

Table 3: Model Fit and Quality Indices

Model Fit and Quality Indices	Fit Criteria	Result	Explanation
Average path coefficient (APC)	P<0.05	0.345, P<0.001	good
Average R-Squared (ARS)	P<0.05	0.609, P<0.001	good
Average Adjusted R-Squared (AARS)	P<0.05	0.599, P<0.001	good
Average block VIF (AVIF)	acceptable if ≤ 5 , ideally ≤ 3.3	2.256	ideal
Average full collinearity VIF (AFVIF)	acceptable if ≤ 5 , ideally ≤ 3.3	2.443	ideal
Tenenhaus GoF (GoF)	small ≥ 0.1 , medium ≥ 0.25 , large ≥ 0.36	0.495	good
Sympson's paradox ratio (SPR)	acceptable if ≥ 0.7 , ideally = 1	1.000,	ideal
R-squared contribution ratio (RSCR)	acceptable if ≥ 0.9 , ideally = 1	1.000,	ideal
Statistical suppression ratio (SSR)	acceptable if ≥ 0.7	1.000,	good
Nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio (NLBCDR)	acceptable if ≥ 0.7	1.000,	good

Table 4: Coefficient of Determination

	R Square
Organizational Commitment	0.532
Performance	0.686

Table 4 shows that the R-square value of Organizational Commitment is 0.532, this means that the contribution of Employee Competence and Employee Empowerment to Organizational Commitment is 53.2%, the R-square value of Performance is 0.686, this means the contribution of Employee Competence, Employee Empowerment and Organizational Commitment to Employee Performance of 68.8%.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 5: Results of the Analysis of Direct Effects Test

Hy p	Relationship between Variables		Path Coefficient	p-value	Explanation
1	Employee Competence	Organizational Commitment	0.304	<0.001	Signifikan
2	Employee Competence	Employee performance	0.330	<0.001	Signifikan
3	Empowerment	Organizational Commitment	0.459	<0.001	Signifikan
4	Empowerment	Employee performance	0.167	0.044	Signifikan
5	Organizational Commitment	Employee performance	0.463	<0.001	Signifikan

Hypothesis 1: Employee Competence has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment.

The direct influence of Employee Competence on Organizational Commitment produces a path coefficient of 0.304 with p-value <0.001. This effect is very significant with a positive sign which means that increasing employee competence will increase organizational commitment. These results indicate that employee competence is a determining factor for organizational commitment.

Hypothesis 2: Employee Competence has a significant effect on Employee Performance.

The direct influence of employee competence on Employee Performance produces a path coefficient of 0.330 with p-value <0.001. This effect is very significant with a positive sign which means that increasing employee competence will increase Employee Performance. These results indicate that employee competence is a determining factor for Employee Performance.

Hypothesis 3: Employee Empowerment has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment.

The direct effect of Employee Empowerment on Organizational Commitment produces a path coefficient of 0.459 with p-value <0.001. This effect is very significant with a positive sign which means that increasing employee empowerment will increase organizational commitment. These results indicate that employee empowerment is a determining factor for organizational commitment.

Hypothesis 4: Employee Empowerment has a significant effect on Employee Performance.

The direct influence of employee empowerment on Employee Performance produces a path coefficient of 0.167 with p-value <0.044. This effect is significant with a positive sign which means that increasing employee empowerment will increase Employee Performance. These results indicate that employee empowerment is a determining factor for Employee Performance

Hypothesis 5: Organizational Commitment has a significant effect on Employee Performance.

The direct influence of employee organizational commitment on employee performance produces a path coefficient of 0.463 with p-value <0.001. This effect is very significant with a positive sign which means that increasing Organizational Commitment will increase Employee Performance. These results indicate that Organizational Commitment is a determining factor for Employee Performance

Table 6: Result of Mediation Effect Testing

Indirect influence test (2 Segment Mediation Variable)					
Explanatory Variable	Mediation Variable	Response variable	Path Coefficient Indirect influence	p-value	Explanation
Employee Competence	Organizational Commitment	Employee performance	0.141	0.022	Variable Mediation
Employee Empowerment	Organizational Commitment	Employee performance	0.213	0.001	Variable Mediation

Hypothesis 6: Organizational Commitment mediates the effect of Employee Competence on Employee Performance.

The path coefficient of the indirect effect of Employee Competence on Employee Performance through the Organizational Commitment variable is 0.141 with a p-value of 0.022. It can be concluded that this indirect effect is significant so that the variable of Organizational Commitment is a mediating variable of the influence of Employee Competence on Employee Performance

Hypothesis 7: Organizational Commitment mediates the effect of Employee Empowerment on Employee Performance

The path coefficient of the indirect effect of Employee Empowerment on Employee Performance through the Organizational Commitment variable is 0.213 with a p-value of 0.001. It can be concluded that this indirect effect is significant so that the variable of Organizational Commitment is a mediating variable of the influence of Employee Empowerment on Employee Performance

DISCUSSION

The study findings show that Employee Competence has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment. Research results are corroborated past studies done by Bani & AlHawary, 2009; Kanfer et al., 2010; Rosa, 2011; Sujana, 2012 Rantesalu et al, 2016 ; Martini et al, 2018 which shows that employee competence has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment. The research findings are supported by the opinion of Thierauf (2008) which states that the competence of human resources is built from the substance of knowledge, skills, experience, attitudes and work skills. High competence is used to increase organizational commitment and individual performance. Employees with good and appropriate competencies will be able to understand what must be done and what their functions are in the job. A good understanding of the function and adequate competence of an employee will foster a high commitment to the organization.

Findings proved that Employee Competence has a significant effect on Employee Performance. These findings are consistent with previous research Lotunani (2014), Rantesalu (2016), Martini (2018) and Renyut (2017) that there is a significant influence between competence and employee performance. The research findings are supported by the opinion of Spencer (2007) that in order to achieve high performance, both for technicians and professionals, salespeople, helping and human service, managers and entrepreneurs are required competencies, which include: achievement and action competence, service competence, leadership competence, management competence. , thinking competence, and effective personality competence.

The study found that Employee Empowerment has a significant effect on Organizational Commitment. Research results are corroborated by past studies done by Raza, et al., 2015; Wadhwa and Verghese, 2015, Gholami et al, 2013; Insan et al, 2013, which explains that companies that carry out empowerment in a continuous workplace will have a good influence on the level of employee commitment, which ultimately makes the organization run effectively. The research results are supported by the opinion of Decicco et al. (2006) that argues that providing opportunities for structural work empowerment for employees (ie empowerment focused on increasing employee engagement) will lead to positive attitudes that encourage employees to achieve commitment to the organization..

Findings proved that Employee Empowerment has a significant effect on Employee Performance. These findings are also in line with the research of Fernandez and Moldogaziev, (2011); Karatepe, 2013; Guest, 2014, Sattar et al., 2015; Guan and Frenkel, 2018; Yin, 2018,

that empowerment has a significant effect on employee performance. The findings of the study are in line with the opinion of Sedarmayanti (2007) that human resource empowerment is a process of business activity to further empower "human resources" through change and human development itself, in the form of abilities, trust, authority, and responsibility and the framework for implementing organizational activities. to improve performance as expected.

Organizational Commitment has a significant effect on Employee Performance. This result is corroborated by the studies done by Ireffin & Mechanic (2014) and Rafiei et al (2014) find evidence that organizational commitment has a significant positive effect on performance. The research findings are supported by the opinion of Sopiah (2008) which says that the higher the organizational commitment, the higher the impact on employees will stay in the organization and will always improve their performance..

The results of the research show that employee competence has a significant positive effect on employee performance through organizational commitment. The positive influence shows that competence is in line with employee performance. This finding provides a contribution that the influence of employee competence on employee performance can be increased through organizational commitment as a mediating variable. The results of this study are in line with the opinion of Sujana (2012) which states that the presence of adequate competence possessed by an employee will foster a high commitment to the organization and have implications for increasing employee performance..

The results of the research show that employee empowerment has a significant positive effect on employee performance through organizational commitment. The positive effect shows that employee empowerment is in line with employee performance. This finding provides a contribution that the effect of employee empowerment on employee performance can be increased through organizational commitment as a mediating variable. The results of this study are in line with the opinion of Wibowo (2012) which states that competence is an ability to do a job that is based on skills and knowledge and is supported by work attitudes, namely experience or learning required by the job. Wibowo also stated that competence is a person's ability to work based on skills and knowledge by including individual attitudes in work. What is also important to support competence is the role of experience and learning in carrying out various duties properly and professionally

CONCLUSION

Employee Competence and Employee Empowerment have a significant and positive effect on Organizational Commitment. This means that the higher the competence and empowerment of employees, the higher the organizational commitment. Employee Competence and Employee Empowerment have a significant and positive effect on employee performance. This means that the higher the competence and empowerment of employees, the higher the employee's performance. Organizational commitment has a significant and positive effect on employee performance. This means that the higher the organizational commitment of employees, the higher the employee's performance.

Organizational commitment mediates the effect of employee competence and employee empowerment on employee performance, this means that the higher the competence and the better the empowerment mediated by the high organizational commitment, the higher employee performance

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